

FUNCTIONAL SYNTAX AND TEXT

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Abstract

This article examines the theoretical foundations of functional syntax and the problems of its application at the text level. Functional syntax involves the analysis of language units taking into account not only grammatical, but also communicative-pragmatic functions. The article emphasizes the importance of this approach in terms of semantic integrity, informative load and the construction of thematic-structural units in the text. The study analyzes the functional foundations of intersentential relations in various types of texts - scientific, artistic and journalistic styles. The functional structure of sentences (theme-rheme relations), communicative types and cases of syntactic variation are considered according to the context. The specific features of the functional approach are revealed based on examples from Turkic languages, especially Azerbaijani and Turkish Turkic. As a result, functional syntax is an important method of language analysis that allows us to understand and interpret the text not only in terms of form, but also in terms of content.

Keywords: functional syntax, syntactic structure of the text, theme-rheme, communicative functions, intersentential connection.

Syntax, one of the main branches of linguistics, studies the structure of language, i.e., how words are combined in sentences and how ideas are expressed. However, in modern linguistics, it is not possible to be satisfied with analyzing only the formal structure. It is also necessary to take into account the functional (i.e., communicative, semantic, and pragmatic) aspects of syntactic units. In this regard, functional syntax has emerged as an important research direction in linguistics since the second half of the 20th century.

The purpose of this study is to examine the basic notions of functional syntax, its difference from classical syntax, and its place and fields of application in modern linguistics.

Functional syntax involves the study of language units not only formally, but also functionally, i.e., in terms of the meaning, intention, and communicative purpose they express. This field analyzes the structure of sentences and the relationship between elements within the purpose of use and the context.

The main research subjects of this field are: the informational structure of the sentence; subject and rheme (theme-rheme) relations; actual division; communicative types; functional loads of syntactic units [1, p. 49].

Functional syntax began to develop in the 1960s–1970s. The main scientific approaches are: Prague School – the theme-rheme theory presented by Wilhelm Matesius and Jan Firbas; Ferdinand de Saussure – explained the interaction of the systemic and functional aspects of language. Halliday (M.A.K.) – put forward the systemic-functional linguistics model and identified three main functions of language (ideational, interpersonal, textual) [6; 7]. One of the main notions of functional syntax is the theory of actual division (thematic-structural division). Here, two main components of the sentence are distinguished: Theme (subject): The part that the speaker or author considers already known. Rheme (new information): The main information transmitted to the listener. For example: “Məktəbli kitab oxuyur” (The schoolboy is reading a book) – In this

sentence, “məktəbli” can be the theme, and “kitab oxuyur” can be the rheme.

Actual division reflects the division of a sentence on a communicative, rather than a structural basis. Functional syntax analyzes each syntactic component according to the following functions: Thematic functions (theme, rheme); communicative functions (interrogative, imperative, predicative); semantic functions (subject, predicate, object, etc.); pragmatic functions (impact on the listener, directionality, etc.)

Theme-rheme relations, informative sentence structures, and sentence models justified in terms of functionally in the Azerbaijani language have been studied.

Functional syntax is one of the important directions of modern linguistics. This approach is not limited to formal structure, but analyzes language units in terms of usage context, purpose, informational loads, and pragmatic impact. Thus, functional syntax serves to clarify not only how language is constructed, but also why it is constructed that way.

This direction occupies an important place not only in academic research, but also in translation theory, artificial intelligence, speech therapy and teaching methodology.

In modern linguistics, the direction of functional syntax, which studies not only the structural features of syntactic units, but also the functional-semantic loads they carry within the text, has gained wide popularity. This field, taking into account the communicative nature of speech, examines the function of sentences and other syntactic units in the text structure. In particular, in Turkic-language texts, it is necessary to study syntactic constructions not only from a formal, but also from a functional and semantic point of view. German linguist S.Schmitz notes in this context: “*Without a functional analysis of syntax, it is impossible to fully understand the communicative purpose of the text*” [14, p. 214].

Functional syntax studies the function that syntactic units of language play in the context and structure of

the text. In this approach, where syntactic units have not only grammatical, but also stylistic, semantic and communicative significance, the main focus is directed the functions of the sentence to transmit information, express attitudes and create relations. Many scholars have conducted research in this field [2; 3; 11; 12].

Turkish linguist G.Engin approaches this field as follows: “When sentences are used in connection with each other, they not only transmit information, but also direct the listener, make them think and encourage them to establish relationships” [4, p.86].

The foundations of functional syntax were developed in G.A.Zolotova’s theory of functional-syntactic categories, T.A. van Dijk’s text linguistics model, and M.A.K. Halliday’s system-function approach. These concepts have been applied to Turkic languages and created the basis for the formation of text-centered syntactic analyses. “Although the sentence, which is the basic unit of communication, expresses a complete idea, the completeness of the idea expressed by it, is relative in nature. A sentence can fully reveal its structural-semantic features in the unity of the sentences surrounding it, in the text environment. The unity of the sentences around a certain idea leads to the creation of a text” [9, p.10].

At the core of the study of functional syntax and text relations is the text linguistics. Text linguistics is one of the broad areas of research in modern linguistics and analyzes how language functions in communication, how it expresses the speaker’s or author’s purpose, and the structure and meaning of the text [8, p. 99]. Syntactic and semantic studies conducted at the classical sentence level have already been extended to the text level and have brought new methods of analysis to the agenda.

Text linguistics encompasses not only written texts, but also oral speech, social media posts, and other forms of communication. This field is of particular importance in terms of understanding communicative intent, evaluating context, and style.

A text is not just a set of sentences, but a logically and semantically whole, connected information structure. The main characteristics of a text are: cohesion: the formal connection of language units; coherence: the connection of meaning and logical sequence; intention: the purpose and intention of the author of the text; situationality: the connection of the text to a specific context.

Text linguistics emerged in the second half of the 20th century. The first serious scientific research in this field was conducted in Europe and America in the 1960s and 1970s. Researchers (for example, Halliday, Hasan, Van Dijk, etc.) paid attention to the syntactic structure of the text, as well as its semantic and pragmatic aspects.

The structure of each text is analyzed in three main aspects: *Formal structure*: Division of parts, introduction-development-conclusion; *Semantic structure*: The relationship of the main idea and additional ideas; *Pragmatic structure*: Impact on the reader and purpose.

The notion of discourse is broader than the notion of text. Text is information in written or oral form, while discourse is a meaningful act of communication

used in a social context. That is, discourse is evaluated together with its context, participants and purpose.

The fields of application of text linguistics are quite wide: *translation theory*; *analysis of religious texts*; *media discourse (TV, newspapers, social media)*; *analysis of legal and administrative documents*; *structure of educational and textbook texts*.

Text linguistics is one of the important directions of modern linguistics and allows to evaluate not only structural, but also functional and contextual aspects of language. This area is an indispensable tool for a deeper study of speech and written communication acts, for a complex study of the human-language relationship.

The practical importance of text linguistics shows that the research conducted in this area can be applied not only in academic, but also in social, legal and educational fields.

When studying a text from a linguistic perspective, the approaches applied can be summarized and divided into three main directions: text grammar, text semantics, and text stylistics [13, p.185]. One of the Azerbaijani linguists, M.G.Seyidov, writes: “The semantic and communicative capabilities of syntactic units within a text depend not only on their structure, but also on their functional load” [15, p.55].

In Turkic languages (Azerbaijani, Turkish, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, etc.), text structure is mainly formed on the basis of the following functional syntactic principles: *thematic beginning*: sentences introducing topic; *expression of opinion and attitude*: expressed by modal and evaluative sentences; *means of cohesion*: syntactic parallelism, lexical repetition, conjunctions; *conclusion function*: the conclusion or result of the content is presented.

For example, in journalistic texts in Turkish Turkic, such a parallel structure is often observed: “*Bu millet sabretti. Bu millet direndi. Bu millet kazandı.*” – here, syntactic parallelism both increases the emotional impact and serves to reinforce the idea.

“The actual processes of the syntax of modern Turkic languages occur within the text. In this respect, syntax is a live process, expressing the dynamics of the development of Turkic languages, such as phonetics, lexis and morphology. Over the past centuries, a large number of syntactic units have been formed, complex syntactic wholes, new types of complex sentences without conjunctions and other syntactic units have appeared” [10, p.49].

There are means of providing structural and semantic coherence between parts of a text. The most important of these are the means of cohesion. *Cohesion* is a means of providing structural and semantic coherence between parts of a text. Scholars divide cohesion into five categories: *reference*, *substitution*, *ellipsis*, *conjunctions*, and *lexical cohesion*.

Means of cohesion — conjunctions, pronouns, lexical repetition, synonymy, intonation and other language units — ensure the structural and semantic unity of the text. Syntactic coherence — relations of subordination and coordination, combined with appropriate conjunctions, strengthen sentence and intra-textual connections. The role of these means in Turkic-language texts is very important both in everyday speech

and in academic writing. In the written language, the structured use of conjunctions and the correct representation of intonation increase coherence; in the oral language, intonation and pauses are of primary importance.

Cohesion devices play a key role in establishing inter-sentential relationships in the text. These devices include the following: *connecting words*: “çünkü” (because), “amma” (but), “halbuki” (however), “buna baxmayaraq” (despite) – create causal and comparative relationships; *syntactic repetitions*: “O, güclü idi. O, inamlı idi. O, xalqına güvənirdi.” (He was strong. He was confident. He trusted his people.) – repetitions draw attention to the topic; *ellipsis and nominal sentences*: Short but meaningful constructions increase expressiveness in the text. Let us give an example from Turkish Turkic: “*Ahmet sabah erkenden kalktı. Çünkü bugün çok önemli bir toplantısı vardı. Önce kahvaltı yaptı, sonra işe gitmek için hazırlandı. İşe vardığında, patronu onu hemen toplantı odasına çağırdı. Toplantı çok verimli geçti ve Ahmet projeyi başarıyla sundu. Böylece herkes onun çalışmasını takdir etti*”.

Here, the words such as “Çünkü”, “Önce”, “sonra”, “daha sonra”, “böylece”, ensure connection between words and sentences, the cohesion of the text. That is, the flow of idea and the content are connected to each other and the text continues in a meaningful way.

Let’s take a look at the example from the Kazakh language: Бауыржан таңертең ерте оянды. Себебі бүгін маңызды емтихан болатын. Ол алдымен таңғы ас ішті, сосын кітаптарын жинап, мектепке баруға дайындалды. Мектепке жеткенде, мұғалімі оны жылы қарсы алды. Емтихан жақсы өтті, сондықтан Бауыржан өте қуанды.

Here, words like “Себебі”, “алдымен”, “сосын”, “сондықтан” provide the flow of the text, the connection of ideas. These words show the cohesion of the text, i.e., the logical connection between sentences.

Turkmen language: *Ahmet irden erten turdy. Sebäbi, bu gün möhümdir bir ýygnaq bar. Ilki bilen nahar etdi, soň işgä gitmäge taýýarlandy. İşgä baransoň, ýolbaşçysy onu ýygnaq otagyna çaýyrdy. Ýygnaq üstünlikli boldy we Ahmet taslamasyny üstünlikli ýetirip bildi. Şonuň üçin hemmeler onuň işini syladylar.*

Words like “Çünkü”, “Әvvälçä”, “Sonra”, “Buna görä” ensure the relationship between words and sentences, and the cohesion of the text. Thus, the meaning of the text is consistent and understandable.

Gagauz language: *Ali sabah erken kalktı. Çünkü bugün önemli bir sınavı vardı. İlk önce kahvaltı yaptı, sonra ders çalışmaya başladı. Okula giderken hava çok güzeldi. Sınav başarılı geçti, bu yüzden Ali çok mutlu oldu.*

In this text, words such as “çünkü”, “әvvälçä”, “sonra”, “buna görä” provide the moral connection between sentences. These words connect the content of the text to each other, making the text fluid and understandable. Thus, the ideas in the text follow each other in a consistent manner and the text has cohesion.

Kyrgyz language: *Бекем эрте менен эрте турду. Анткени бүгүн маанилүү экзамен бар эле. Ал биринчи тамак жеди, андан кийин китептерин*

даярдады. Мектепке барганда, мугалими аны жылуу кабыл алды. Экзамен ийгиликтүү өттү, ошондуктан Бекем абдан кубанды.

In this text, words such as “Çünkü”, “ilk olaraq”, “ondan sonra”, “buna görä” create meaning connections between sentences. These words make the content of the text stable and consistent, making it understandable and of high quality. Thus, the ideas and thoughts within the text are closely related to each other and the text has cohesion.

“Linguistic analysis of the text is mainly carried out in two directions. First, in the direction of describing functional-semantic types as a structural unit of speech, and second, in the direction of classifying and describing a complex syntactic whole” [5, p.85].

For example, from the speech of a speaker in Kazakh Turkic: “Bүgүн – sabır. Erte – ümit. Yarın – zafer.” – here nominal sentences and parallelism show the rhythmic and semantic value that functional syntax gives to the text.

In Turkish-language literary texts, functional syntactic methods serve to increase imagery and emotionality. Inversion, ellipsis, and syntactic parallelism are used in these texts. *Inversion*: is used to emphasize an idea; *ellipsis*: creates a short expression, tension, and emotional flow; *syntactic parallelism*: creates repetition and artistic harmony.

For example, Orkhan Veli Kanık writes: “Ne vakit bir yaşamak düşünsem / Bu kurtlar sofrasında belki zor / Ayıpsız ama ellerimiz de değil.” – here syntactic fragmentation and metaphorical inversion create profound meanings.

Let’s look at inversion in a text fragment in Turkmen: *Gözellik dünýäni bezäpdir. Täze çemenler deňizň kenarynda açylypdyr. Diňe günorta hem ýyly, hem ýel çykdy. Güllemek başlady çagalar.*

Gelir bahar yavaş-yavaş köylere. Uyanır toprak, yeşillenir dağlar. Sevinc ile dolar insanın yüreği. Güzел olur her şey, başka görünür dünya.

Inversion, i.e., a change in the usual (standard) syntactic order of words in this text is observed. For example:

In the sentence “Gelir bahar yavaş-yavaş köylere”, the usual word order should have been “Bahar yavaş-yavaş köylere gelir”. Here, placing the verb “Gelir” at the beginning of the sentence adds poetic emphasis to the idea and makes the expression emotional. Instead of “Sevinc ile dolar insanın yüreği”, it was expected to say “İnsanın yüreği sevinc ile dolar” as standard. However, changing the word order gives the sentence an artistic effect. Such inversions are widely used in the Gagauz literary language, especially in literary texts and poetry. The purpose is either to create emphasis or to make the expression more fluid and emotional.

In this text, the words are placed at the beginning in a way that is different from the usual arrangement. For example, in the sentence “Gözellik dünýäni bezäpdir”, the word “Gözellik” is placed at the beginning of the sentence and gains special emphasis. Thus, the idea becomes stronger and the text seems more effective.

“Conceptual information has a special place in the text, it is undoubtedly of a complex nature. Thus, this

information is directly related to the general idea of the text and is unevenly distributed throughout the text" [10, p.59].

The function of syntactic structures in the scientific style is mainly logical consistency and accurate delivery of information. Here: compound sentences prevail; cause and effect relationships are expressed; syntactic completeness and consistency are maintained.

"Functional syntax is a field that studies the communicative load of syntactic units, their semantic capabilities within the text." – here the completeness and consistency of information are key points. "The problem of the text being a larger complex unit than a sentence is one of the main linguistic problems of the last decade of the 20th century. Although the issue of the text having a special structure, grammatical and semantic features has begun to interest linguists in recent times, ideas related to text syntax were expressed as early as the 19th century. As a whole, text linguistics as a scientific field began to take shape in the late 19th and early 20th centuries" [13, p.123].

Research shows that functional syntax in Turkic-language texts provides a systematic use of language tools necessary for the realization of communicative goals in the text. The functional capabilities of syntactic structures are determined not only by their form, but also by the semantic and stylistic loads they carry within the text.

Future research in this area should be focused on discourse analysis, pragmatic aspects of functional syntax and its role in the translation process.

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